

RAYLEIGH-RITZ ANALYSIS OF ANGLE-PLY THICK LAMINATES OF
BIMODULUS COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Both the Rayleigh-Ritz and Finite-Layer Methods[1] are used in this paper to analyse the bending problem of angle-ply thick laminates of bimodulus composite materials with simply supported boundary conditions, and effects of various parameters on the nondimensional center deflections are also studied.

Keywords: bimodulus, composite, material, angle-ply laminates, Rayleigh-Ritz Method, Finite-Layers Method

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the important characteristics of some fiber-reinforced composites is that they often behave different elastic moduli under simple tension and simple compression. Their stress-strain characteristic is actually curvilinear and is usually approximated by bilinear model. Such a material is called a bimodulus composite material.

The bending and vibration problems of bimodulus material laminates have been studied by many people, but their analyses are limited to thin plate problems. Bert, et al. are believed to be the first ones to study the bending and vibration problems of thick rectangular bimodulus composite plates. To the best of the authors' knowledge, previous analyses of thick bimodulus material laminates are limited to cross-ply laminates. There has been no literature on investigation for angle-ply thick laminates of bimodulus composite materials. It is quite difficult to select one elastic modulus (either tensile or compressive) to analyze thick angle-ply laminates of bimodulus composite materials.

In this paper, the bending behavior of angle-ply thick laminates for bimodulus material with simply supported boundary conditions is analysed by both Rayleigh-Ritz and Finite-Layer Methods. The effects of various parameters, such as orthotropic ratio(E_1/E_2), multimodulus ratio(E_t/E_c), aspect ratio(a/b) and fiber direction (θ) on the center deflections of bimodulus angle-ply laminates are discussed. Our solutions are compared with numerical results existing in the literature for special cases(for $\theta=0$ [2], and $E_t/E_c=1$ [3]) and a good agreement is obtained

2. FORMULATION

2.1 Total Potential Energy and Strain Energy

By the YNS theory , the displacement field is given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u(x,y,z) &= u^*(x,y) + z \psi_x(x,y) \\
 v(x,y,z) &= v^*(x,y) + z \psi_y(x,y) \\
 w(x,y,z) &= w^*(x,y)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

Where u , v and w is the displacements along x , y and z direction respectively, and u^* , v^* are the in-plane displacements of the mid-plane, ψ_x and ψ_y are the shear rotations.

The total potential energy Π is

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Pi &= U - W \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \int_V (\sigma_x \epsilon_x + \sigma_y \epsilon_y + \tau_{xy} \gamma_{xy} + \tau_{xz} \gamma_{xz} + \tau_{yz} \gamma_{yz}) dx dy dz - \int_R q w^* dx dy - \int_{C_1} \hat{N}_n u_n^* ds \\
 &\quad - \int_{C_2} \hat{N}_s u_s^* ds - \int_{C_3} \hat{M}_n \psi_n ds - \int_{C_4} \hat{M}_s \psi_s ds - \int_{C_5} \hat{Q}_n w^* ds
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2}$$

Where C_i ($i=1,2,\dots,5$) are the portions of the boundary of the midplane R , on which N_n, N_s, M_n, M_s and Q_n are specified respectively.

The strain energy U of the plate is

$$\begin{aligned}
 U &= \frac{1}{2} \int_V (\sigma_x \epsilon_x + \sigma_y \epsilon_y + \tau_{xy} \gamma_{xy} + \tau_{xz} \gamma_{xz} + \tau_{yz} \gamma_{yz}) dx dy dz \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \iint \{ A_{11}(u_{,x}^*)^2 + 2A_{12}u_{,x}^*v_{,y}^* + A_{22}(v_{,y}^*)^2 + 2A_{16}(u_{,y}^* + v_{,x}^*)u_{,x}^* + 2A_{26}(u_{,y}^* + v_{,x}^*)v_{,y}^* \\
 &\quad + A_{66}(u_{,y}^* + v_{,x}^*)^2 + 2B_{11}\psi_{x,x}^* + 2B_{12}(\psi_{y,y}u_{,x}^* + \psi_{x,x}v_{,y}^*) + 2B_{22}\psi_{y,y}v_{,y}^* + 2B_{16}(\psi_{x,y}u_{,x}^* \\
 &\quad + \psi_{y,x}u_{,x}^* + \psi_{x,x}u_{,y}^* + \psi_{x,x}v_{,x}^*) + 2B_{26}(\psi_{x,y}v_{,y}^* + \psi_{y,x}v_{,y}^* + \psi_{y,y}u_{,y}^* + \psi_{y,y}v_{,x}^*) \\
 &\quad + 2B_{66}(\psi_{x,y} + \psi_{y,x})(u_{,y}^* + v_{,x}^*) + A_{44}(w_{,y}^* + \psi_y^*)^2 + 2A_{45}[(w_{,x}^* + \psi_x^*)(\psi_y^* + w_{,y}^*)] + A_{55}(w_{,x}^* + \psi_y^*)^2 \\
 &\quad + D_{11}(\psi_{x,x}^*)^2 + 2D_{12}\psi_{y,y}\psi_{x,x}^* + D_{22}(\psi_{y,y}^*)^2 + 2D_{16}\psi_{x,x}(\psi_{x,y} + \psi_{y,x}^*) + 2D_{26}\psi_{y,y}(\psi_{x,y} + \psi_{y,x}^*) \\
 &\quad + D_{66}(\psi_{x,y} + \psi_{y,x}^*)^2 \} dx dy
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3}$$

Here A_{ij} , B_{ij} , D_{ij} are laminate stiffnesses

$$\begin{aligned}
 (A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij}) &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} Q_{ij}^{(m)}(1, z, z^2) dz \quad (i,j=1,2,6) \\
 A_{ij} &= k_a k_b \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} Q_{ij}^{(m)} dz \quad (i,j= 4,5, \alpha=6-i, \beta=6-j)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4}$$

Where $Q_{ij}^{(m)}$ are the reduced stiffnesses of the m th layer, k_a are the shear correction coefficients, $k = k_1 k_2 = k_1^2 = k_2^2$.

2.2. Rayleigh-Ritz Solution under Simply Supported Boundary Conditions

The following simply supported boundary conditions are considered:

$$x=0, a: v^* = N_x = w^* = \psi_y = M_x = 0$$

$$y=0, b: u' = N_x = w' = \psi_x = M_x = 0 \quad (5)$$

We assume that the applied transverse load q can be expanded in following double-Fourier series

$$q = \sum_{m,n=1}^{\infty} Q_{mn} \sin \alpha x \sin \beta y \quad (6)$$

Where $\alpha = m\pi/a$, $\beta = n\pi/b$

If there are no boundary forces, then w is equal to $\int_{\mathbb{R}} q w' dx dy$ in (2). The Rayleigh-Ritz solution satisfied the boundary conditions (5) is

$$\begin{aligned} u' &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} U_{mn} \cos \alpha x \sin \beta y \\ v' &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} V_{mn} \sin \alpha x \cos \beta y \\ w' &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} W_{mn} \sin \alpha x \sin \beta y \\ \psi_y &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} Y_{mn} \sin \alpha x \cos \beta y \\ \psi_x &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_{mn} \cos \alpha x \sin \beta y \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

By well-known Rayleigh-Ritz technique, the following linear equation set is obtained.

$$[K] \{ \delta \} = \{ F \} \quad (8)$$

In this equation set, U_{mn} , V_{mn} , W_{mn} , Y_{mn} and X_{mn} are contained in $\{ \delta \}$ and should be determined. By solving this equation set, the Rayleigh-Ritz solution can be obtained.

2.3. Selection of Elastic Modulus and Finite-Layer Method

The selection of elastic modulus depends on whether the fiber-direction strain is tensile or compressive [3]. By transformation of coordinates the fiber-direction strain ϵ_L is

$$\epsilon_L = c^2 \epsilon_x + s^2 \epsilon_y + cs \gamma_{xy} \quad (9)$$

Where $c = \cos \theta$, $s = \sin \theta$, θ is the angle between fiber-direction and x axis.

If $m=n=1$, from (7), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_x &= -(U_{11} + ZX_{11}) \frac{\pi}{a} \sin \frac{\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{\pi y}{b} \\ \epsilon_y &= -(V_{11} + ZY_{11}) \frac{\pi}{b} \sin \frac{\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{\pi y}{b} \\ \gamma_{xy} &= (U_{11} \frac{\pi}{b} + V_{11} \frac{\pi}{a} + ZX_{11} \frac{\pi}{b} + ZY_{11} \frac{\pi}{a}) \cos \frac{\pi x}{a} \cos \frac{\pi y}{b} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

It is noted that ϵ_L is a function of x , y , z and a linear function of z as well. We can calculate the stiffnesses of laminate by Finite-Layers Method. We divide the laminate along z direction into many sublayers parallel to the midplane in such way, so that the variation of ϵ_L along z direction in each sublayers can be neglected (for example, to divide a two-layer laminate into 20 sublayers). For every sublayer, the ϵ_L is calculated by the mean value of ϵ_L at 3×3 Gauss sampling points. By superimposing the stiffnesses of all sublayers, the total stiffnesses of the laminates are obtained. An iteration procedure is required for this calculation.

3 NUMERICAL RESULTS

In the following, we present numerical results for bending analysis of antisymmetric angle-ply laminates of bimodulus composite materials. The following two sets of material properties are employed. Material 1 (Aramid-Rubber):

$$E_{1t}=3.580\text{Gpa}, E_{2t}=0.00909\text{Gpa}, G_{12t}=0.00370\text{Gpa}, G_{23t}=0.00290\text{Gpa}, \nu_{12t}=0.416, \\ E_{1c}=0.012\text{Gpa}, E_{2c}=0.01200\text{Gpa}, G_{12c}=0.00370\text{Gpa}, G_{23c}=0.00499\text{Gpa}, \nu_{12c}=0.205$$

Where the subscripts t and c denote tensile modulus and compressive modulus respectively. Material 2:

$$E_1/E_2=40, G_{12}/E_2=0.6, E_{23}/E_2=0.5, \nu_{12}=0.25, \nu_{13}=\nu_{12}, G_{13}=G_{12}, E_t/E_c=1.2$$

For Material 2, when the effects of E_1/E_2 on the deflection are considered, we take $E_t/E_c=1.2$, and when the effects of E_t/E_c on the deflection are considered, we take $E_1/E_2=40$.

The normal pressure load is taken as sinusoidally distributed.

$$q=q_0 \sin \frac{\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{\pi y}{b} \tag{11}$$

The center deflections are non-dimensionalized as follows.

$$\bar{w} = w \left(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{b}{2}, 0 \right) E_{2c} h^3 / (q_0 b^4) \tag{12}$$

Because there is no analysis available for angle-ply bimodulus thick laminates, the solutions obtained here are estimated in the following two special cases.

Numerical results for single-layer square laminate with the fiber oriented parallel to x axis, which is obtained from antisymmetric angle-ply laminates ($\theta/-\theta \dots$) with $\theta=0$, and the results for $E_t/E_c=1$ are compared with the corresponding Bert's solution [2] and Reddy's solution [3], respectively, as shown in Table 1 and Table 2. Upon comparison of various results, we find that the agreement is good. The Rayleigh-Ritz solutions are smaller than Bert's and Reddy's exact solutions. As the aspect ratio is larger, the difference between the solution is less.

It is noted that the nondimensional center deflection is increased due to increase of the aspect ratio, and it is decreased as the width-thickness ratio is increased. The variation of nondimensional center deflection with lamination angle θ , orthotropic ratio (E_1/E_2) and multimodulus ratio (E_t/E_c) are shown in Fig1-Fig3 respectively. It is shown that as θ , E_1/E_2 and E_t/E_c is increased the deflection is decreased too. The minimum nondimensional deflection appears at $\theta = 45^\circ$.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results discussed above, the following conclusions about thick angle-ply laminates of bimodulus materials can be obtained:

- (1) The solution processing by using Rayleigh-Ritz Method and Finite-Layer Method is effective.
- (2) The nondimensional center deflection is increased as the aspect ratio is increased.
- (3) The nondimensional center deflection is decreased as the orthotropic ratio, width-thickness ratio, multimodulus ratio and lamination angle (up to 45°) is increased.

Table 1. Nondimensional center deflections for single-layer 0° Aramid-Rubber laminates ($a/h=10, a/b=1$)

a/b	Bert[2]	present
0.7	0.00739	0.00625
0.9	0.01545	0.01387
1.0	0.02046	0.01868
1.2	0.03160	0.02950
1.4	0.04313	0.04075
1.6	0.05406	0.05151
1.8	0.06390	0.06154
2.0	0.07250	0.06997

Fig.1. Effect of lamination angle on the nondimensional center deflection of 10-layer antisymmetric angle-ply laminates ($a/b=1, a/h=10$, material 2)

Fig.2. Effect of orthotropic ratio on the nondimensional center deflection of 10-layer antisymmetric angle-ply laminates($a/b=1$, $a/h=10$, $\theta=15^\circ$, material 2)

Table 2. Nondimensional center deflections for 10-layer angle-ply laminates($a/b=1$, $\theta=30^\circ$, material 2)

a/h	Reddy [3]	present
5	6.316	6.278
10	2.872	2.861
20	2.005	2.000
25	1.900	1.897
50	1.761	1.759

Fig.3. Effect of multimodulus ratio on the nondimensional center deflection of 10-layer antisymmetric angle-ply laminates($a/b=1$, $a/h=10$, $\theta=15^\circ$, material 2)

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References

1. Zhang Genquan, Tsun-Kuei Wang, ACTA MATERIAE COMPOSITAE vol.9, No.1, 1992, p92
2. Bert, C.W, etal, AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS 21st Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, Seattle, May 12-14, 1980, part 1, p177
3. J.N.Reddy and W.C. Chao, Nuclear Engineering and Design Vol. 64, 1981, p153

REPAIR

